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New finds of *Urophora dzieduszyckii* Frauenfeld, 1867 (Diptera: Tephritidae)

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Urophora dzieduszyckii for one and a half century remained an enigmatic European species of the family Tephritidae (Diptera); it has been already included to the Red Book of Ukraine (Korneyev, 2009) based only on a collection material from a single locality in Synkiv and believed to be either an extinct, or extant very locally. Recently, it was rediscovered and photographed in several localities in Ternopil and Chernivtsi Region on plants of *Echinops exaltatus* (Korneyev et al., 2016 a, b, 2019, 2021).

New observations on this species were made by the authors in 2021–2022 and published on UkrBIN (2022), of them two in the Medobory Nature Reserve (49.1827N, 26.1949E, 29.06.2022, N. Shymkiv, 49.1824N, 26.1953E, 05.07.2022, N. Shymkiv & H. Baranchuk) and Banyliv-Pidhirnyi (48.045066N, 25.44652E, 17.07.2021, V.Shparyk & A.Zamoroka) are by far the northernmost and southernmost localities in Ukraine, correspondingly. They considerably extend currently known range of this protected species in Ukraine.

Figs 1–4. *Urophora dzieduszyckii*: 1 — mating couple on a flower head; 2 — female feeding on honey dew (photo by N. Shupliak); 3 — map of known records in Ternopil and Chernivtsi Regions of Ukraine (generated from UkrBIN database); 4 — host plant, *Echinops exaltatus*.

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